

ANALISIS SISTEM INFORMASI JADWAL TERPADU BERBASIS WEBSITE

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian adalah menganalisis sistem informasi jadwal terpadu di Program Studi Pendidikan Teknologi Informasi dan Komputer (PTIK) IKIP PGRI Pontianak. Metode penelitian adalah deskriptif kualitatif. Subjek penelitian berjumlah 15 orang yang terdiri dari 10 mahasiswa, 4 dosen, dan 1 staf Program Studi PTIK. Alat pengumpulan data menggunakan wawancara dengan teknik pengumpul data menggunakan panduan wawancara. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif kualitatif. Analisis Sistem Jadwal Terpadu Program Studi PTIK yang dilakukan meliputi jadwal perkuliahan, jadwal dosen pembimbing skripsi, serta jadwal seminar dan skripsi. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan: (1) sistem berjalan yang digunakan tidak memiliki karakteristik *usability*, *functionality*, dan *visual communication*; dan (2) usulan sistem yang baru berbentuk alur program dengan memperhatikan karakteristik *usability*, *functionality*, dan *visual communication*.

Kata Kunci: sistem informasi, *database*, jadwal terpadu.

Abstract

The purpose of the research was to analyze the integrated schedule information system in the Computer and Information Technology Education Study Program (PTIK) IKIP PGRI Pontianak. The research method used descriptive qualitative. The research subjects were 15 people consisting of 10 students, 4 lecturers, and 1 staff of the PTIK Study Program. Data collection tools used interviews with data collection techniques used interview guides. The data analysis technique used a qualitative descriptive analysis. Analysis of the integrated schedule system of the PTIK Study Program which is carried out includes lecture schedules, thesis supervisor schedules, and seminars or thesis schedules. The results of the research were: (1) the running system used did not have the characteristics of usability, functionality, and visual communication; and (2) the proposed new system is in the form of a program flow by taking into account the characteristics of usability, functionality, and visual communication.

Keywords: information system, *database*, integrated schedule.